

Solvent Extraction and Determination of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) with Pyridines in Thiocyanate System[†]

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Solvent-extraction and spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} as pyridine/ α -pic/ β pic/ γ -pic/2 : 4 : 6-collidine thiocyanates, and extractive-gravimetric determination of Ni^{II} as pyridine/ β -pic/ γ -pic thiocyanate have been described. Ni^{II} does not form complexes in presence of thiocyanate when the methyl group is in the 2-position of the pyridine ring. So, α -pic and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine have been used for the separation of Ni^{II} from Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pd^{II}.

SOLVENT extraction and spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions using thiocyanate ion as a complexing agent is well known. Various amines, especially of high molecular weight, and organic bases have been reported for liquid-liquid extraction of many metals^{1,2}. Tertiary amines have been found to be very useful for this purpose. Spectrophotometric determination as mixed complexes of Cu^{II}, V^{II} and Fe^{II}-thiocyanate and amines with a pyridine nucleus have also been reported³⁻⁵ recently. But no work has been attempted so far to determine trace amounts of Pd^{II} as mixed complexes using thiocyanate ion and various methyl substituted pyridines. Recently, Pd^{II} was gravimetrically estimated⁶ as mixed complexes with 2,4- and 2,6-lutidine and thiocyanate ion. Pd^{II}-thiocyanate forms colourless complexes, soluble in chloroform with py/ α -pic/ β -pic/ γ -pic/2 : 4 : 6-collidine in thiocyanate system. The present communication deals with the solvent extraction studies of these complexes. Ni^{II} thiocyanate forms similar complexes with py/ β -pic/ γ -pic, but not with α -pic and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine. Therefore, α -pic and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine have been used to separate mixtures of trace amounts of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} and thereby estimating both quantitatively.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of either A.R. or C.P. grades unless otherwise mentioned. Distilled CHCl₃ (E. Merck), pyridine (Poland), α -pic (Riedel), β -pic (B.D.H.), γ -pic (B.D.H.) and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine (B.D.H.) were used. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving known amounts of the corresponding pure salts in distilled water or dilute HCl. NH₄SCN (E. Merck), PdCl₂ (Chempure) and NiCl₂ (B.D.H.) were standardised by usual methods⁷.

Apparatus : An ECL 5651 digital pH meter was used to record pH. A Beckman DU-2 spectro-

photometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

Procedure :

For palladium : An aliquot of Pd^{II} solution containing 15-106.9 μ g of the metal was placed in a separating funnel and 1.5 ml of 2% (w/v) NH₄SCN solution was mixed, followed by addition of 0.5 ml α -pic. pH of the solution was adjusted with dilute HCl and the volume was made upto 20 ml by distilled water, and then it was equilibrated with 20 ml CHCl₃ by manual shaking for 5 min. The absorbance of the CHCl₃-extract was measured against a reagent blank prepared under identical condition. For other picolines and pyridine the same procedure, as described above, was followed⁸.

For nickel : An aliquot containing 10-50 mg of Ni^{II} was placed in a separating funnel. To this solution was added 3.0 ml of 2% (w/v) aqueous NH₄SCN followed by addition of calculated amount of py/ β -pic/ γ -pic. Volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 15 ml with distilled water and suitable pH value was attained with the help of buffer solutions. Finally, 25 ml CHCl₃ was added and the funnel was shaken vigorously for 5 min. Sky-blue coloured organic extract was drained out. It was then evaporated followed by digestion with HClO₄ : HNO₃ (1 : 5) mixture, the metal content in the extract was determined gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime.

Results and Discussion

pH of the solution plays an important role in this type of extractive studies. Results are presented in the Table 1. Complete extraction (\approx 100%) of the metals in the respective systems is only possible in the pH ranges indicated in the table.

Beer's law was found to be valid within the ranges 0.8-7.7, 0.4-4.52, 0.5-5.5, 0.5-5.5 and 0.5-5.5 μ g Pd^{II}/ml CHCl₃ for py, α -pic, β -pic, γ -pic and

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH

Metal	Pyridine	α -pic	β -pic	γ -pic	2 : 4 : 6-Collidine
Pd ^{II}	4.9-7.1	3.5-7.0	2.6-5.8	4.9-6.6	1.2-2.1
Ni ^{II}	5.0-6.8		4.5-6.5	4.5-5.2	

2 : 4 : 6-collidine, respectively. 8.98-49.38 mg Ni^{II}/ml CHCl₃ could be estimated quite confidently using py, β -pic and γ -pic. Sandell's sensitivities range from 0.0042-0.0076 μ g Pd^{II} cm⁻² and molar absorptivities lie in the range (1.39-3.21) $\times 10^4$ dm² mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

The extent of extraction was studied with different amount of py (0.099-0.69 g) and picolines (2.8-0.95 g), and also with different amount of aqueous NH₄SCN. 8 mg of py/pic quantitatively extracts each mg of Ni^{II} in presence of 0.5 ml of 2% (w/v) aqueous NH₄SCN in the pH ranges mentioned earlier. Higher concentrations (1 ml for organic reagents and 1.3 ml for 2% (w/v) aqueous NH₄SCN) did not affect the extraction, but was avoided because of reagent economy.

Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} were extracted quantitatively into the organic layer in a single operation when the layers were shaken for 5-10 min.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of diverse ions in the determination of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} was studied as described in the recommended procedures. An ion was considered to interfere if the weight of the metal chelate/absorbance obtained differed by more than $\pm 2\%$ from that for the actual calculated value. In each case 20-50 mg Ni^{II} was tested with py/ β -pic/ γ -pic and thiocyanate in presence of a number of commonly associated cations and anions. Foreign ions were added prior to the addition of the reagent solution and pH value was adjusted. In case of Pd^{II}, 40-100 μ g Pd^{II} was extracted and determined in the presence of about 10 mg of foreign ions except in the cases of Rh^{III} (1.96 mg), Pt^{IV} (1.0 mg), Cd^{II} (3.2 mg), F⁻ (4.5 mg), Br⁻ (5.8 mg), I⁻ (8.2 mg) and EDTA (4 mg) where more than the amount indicated in the brackets caused serious interference⁹. In both the cases Fe^{III} interferes, and this obstruction was removed by using an excess of citrate ions with which Fe^{III} forms complex ion. 3-4 g of tripotassium citrate renders about 75 mg of Fe^{III} harmless. The following ions, added as nitrate, sulphate or chloride caused no interference at M : Ni weight ratio given :

Zn^{II} ≥ 13 , Cd^{II} ≥ 12 , Hg^{II} ≤ 0.5 , Ag^I ≤ 0.2 ,
 Be^{II} ≥ 14 , Al^{III} ≥ 15 , Th^{IV} ≤ 0.1 , U^{VI}O₂ ≥ 8 ,
 Pt^{IV} ≤ 5 , Rh^{III} ≤ 3 , La^{III} ≥ 15 , Sr^{II} ≥ 13 ,
 Ba^{II} ≥ 12 , Zr^{IV} ≥ 11 , Mn^{II} ≥ 11 , Ca^{II} ≥ 15 ,
 Mg^{II} ≥ 10 , V^{IV} ≤ 1 , and alkali metals ≥ 20 .

Among anions, phosphate, acetate, fluoride, bromide, iodide, molybdate, tartrate, citrate, borate (added as alkali salts) do not interfere even where their weight ratio is at least 10-15 times that of Ni. The anions like EDTA and oxalate interfered by completely preventing colour formation. This may be due to the fact that Ni^{II} has a greater affinity for these complexing agents compared to the organic bases used for estimation. Ni^{II} fails to form complexes with α -substituted pyridine in thiocyanate system under the recommended conditions; so α -pic and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine could be used to separate Ni^{II} from Pd^{II} without using any other masking agents. 3d⁸ orbital of Ni^{II} probably fails to accommodate 2-substituted pyridines because of steric repulsion; similar steric repulsion of comparable degree does not occur in case of Pd^{II} probably owing to larger size of 4d⁸ orbital. Ammonium bifluoride was used to avoid interference due to Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} in 2 : 4 : 6-collidine-SCN system, and in the same system Pt^{IV} also co-extracted with Pd^{II}. As 2 : 4 : 6-collidine-SCN requires relatively highly acidic medium (pH 1.2-2.1) for quantitative extraction of the metal this system apparently differs markedly from the remaining four systems. In case of Pd^{II}, molybdate and thiosulphate interfered seriously with every systems. Details of the separation of Ni^{II} from Pd^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} have been discussed elsewhere^{9,10}.

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